

ŚLĄSKI KWARTALNIK HISTORYCZNY SOBÓTKA

NOT ONLY THE REFORMATION.
CHURCHES AND RELIGIOUS MOVEMENTS IN SILESIA
THROUGH THE CENTURIES

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CULTURAL CONTENT OF OUTSTANDING WORKS OF SACRED ARCHITECTURE IN SILESIA IN THE YEARS 1945–2015

ABSTRACT: The aim of the article is to present the relationship between the elements of the artistic form of church buildings and their political sources. The most important churches built in 1945–2015 were associated with ideological changes in the communist state and then with social life after communism.

KEYWORDS: sacred architecture, church history in the 20th century, communism in Poland

The issue of architecture as a carrier of cultural content aroused serious controversy at the end of the 1960s, when critical analysis of iconology appeared in the history of art, an interpretative method developed in the works of Erwin Panofsky. The doctrine of the German-American erudite assumed that works of art could convey ideological content appropriate to the environment in which the artists were active.

In this spirit, inter alia, Panofsky interpreted the subsequent stages of the development of Gothic sacred architecture as being fully adequate to the divisions occurring in the history of scholasticism. The approach characteristic of this scholar's research was not new in the history of art and was preceded by the work of Max Dvořák, who quite directly adapted the philosophy of Hegel and assumed that all works of art of a given period pervade the same "spirit of time". Premises of the position assuming that architecture has the possibility of symbolic or metaphorical reference to the outside world and the content contained in religious,

philosophical or literary texts may also be indicated in many earlier times. In the theories of the so-called Revolutionary architects, Claude Nicolas Ledoux, Étienne-Louis Boullée and Jean-Jacques Lequeu, the concept of “architecture parlante” was developed which assumed the necessity of using a specific set of forms and decorations corresponding to the functional purpose of the building. The rich decoration of facades of architectural objects with full figural sculptures and bas-reliefs, creating rich and complex message content, occurred earlier in the Baroque, Gothic architecture and also in the manifestations of the architecture of the Ancient Near East. This long-lasting tradition was questioned only in the architecture of radical modernism, which tended to use primarily geometrical forms, generally devoid of any applied decorations. The exception was the reference to elements of transoceanic ships and machines. The renewal of the custom of referring to the shapes of the outside world returned in the 1970s in postmodern architecture, which was also referred to as a narrative.

The review of the phenomenon of using architectural objects as carriers of information indicates that we are dealing with a tradition that goes on and on in a historically very distant era, a history in which limitations noticed by the critics should be taken into account. Certainly, it can no longer be assumed that building objects are ideologically connected with the intellectual trends prevailing at a given time.

However, the argument that assuming the penetration of works of art by spiritual phenomena have been questioned in a convincing way, it can't be denied that artistic objects can be used consciously for propagating specific meanings, or that a correct understanding of their aesthetic values also requires knowledge surrounding the circumstances of their production. It is especially difficult to deny that perception of the work is influenced by historical information linking its creation with the facts of political or religious life. The user of a sacred object, even a passing tourist, feels a culturally-educated need to acquire knowledge about the nature and history of the object visited. Also, the faithful using the church for religious purposes build their personal attitude towards it based on the basic facts of its history. The interested person is introduced to the descriptions of situations in which specific buildings were created, through the use of information plaques decorating historic objects, guides, websites, and often special occasional publications informing of the past history of the work. Therefore, it can't be denied that knowledge of this kind is a component of the perception of an artistic object. Relations between history and artistic form can't be understood as deeply internal

and structural, however, it is justified to present them as elements complementing the general reception of construction work.

The history of sacral buildings in the first years after 1945 was marked by the stigma of war destruction on the one hand, and, on the other hand, by the change of the political system and the construction of the communist dictatorship. Particularly characteristic for this period are the fate of the cathedrals in Wrocław and Katowice. After the announcement in August 1944 of the fortress of Wrocław (Festung Breslau) for several months, the city's residents could not yet feel the horror of war. On 17 and 18 January 1945, the Soviet air forces bombed the Wrocław railway stations. In the first days of February, for the first time the city was shelled by artillery, on the night of 15 to 16 February it was surrounded, while at the same time there was ongoing fighting in the outskirts, and subsequently the outer districts were occupied by the Russians. On 22 February a massive attack from the south began.

The assault from the western side began on 1 April, while on 2 April 1945, part of the 750 Soviet aircraft taking part in the air raids bombed Cathedral Island (Ostrów Tumski) and destroyed the cathedral. As he wrote in his memoirs, Fr. Paul Peikert, then parish priest of Saint Maurice, an earlier raid of 27 March touched the building: "The cathedral received a heavy blow from the bomb, which fell on the southern side nave and pierced it. The presbytery of The Holy Cross was also hit by the bomb. The elevated building of the church of The Holy Cross looks like a widow in mourning. You can't recognize Wrocław anymore"¹.

On Easter Monday, 2 April, the burning vaults of the front facade towers fell on the roof of the nave and led to its destruction. Peikert also saw it from the nearby Kaiserbrücke and noted: "Flames burst from the towers of the cathedral church; the roof of the Cathedral was one sea of flames"². Destruction also affected the side aisles and the presbytery section³.

A few months later, after the end of warfare, in September 1945, the cathedral was visited by a new apostolic administrator of the archdiocese of Wrocław, Fr. Dr. Karol Milik and found there the heap of brick debris. In his memoirs of 1 September he wrote: "In the afternoon I visit the mother of the Silesian

¹ Paul Peikert, *Kronika dni oblężenia. Wrocław 22 I – 6 V 1945*, Wrocław 1964, p. 129.

² *Ibidem*, p. 158

³ Marcin Bukowski, *Katedra wrocławska. Architektura – rozwój – zniszczenie – odbudowa*, Wrocław 1962, p. 122; Aleksandra Marcinów, *Wokół problemów odbudowy katedry wrocławskiej*, [in:] *Katedra wrocławska na przestrzeni tysiąclecia. Studia z historii architektury i sztuki*, eds. Romuald Kaczmarek, Dariusz Galewski, Wrocław 2016, p. 317.

churches – the cathedral. I go inside her, I look up – the blue firmament is her roof and the vault. Scarred walls protrude around them”⁴. In the spring of the following year, as a result of water saturation, the vaults of the nave eventually collapsed. It happened as if against the determination of Fr. Milik, who noted his pledge in his diary: “I kneel on the ruins of the cathedral and vow to rebuild it and return to its former beauty”⁵. When, after the end of warfare, the thought of demolishing the ruined building was considered, the concept of its reconstruction won. In the second quarter of 1946, an institution was established to deal with the reconstruction of selected buildings in Wrocław, and at that time the facility at Ostrów Tumski was included among them. The architect Marcin Bukowski was appointed head of reconstruction, he also oversaw over the next few years the rise of Wrocław Town Hall from the ruins. The reconstruction plan was to be implemented in several stages, the first of which began on 15 November 1946⁶. The walls, roof and part of the vaults were rebuilt by February 1949.

The beginning of 1951 was marked by the serious interference by state authorities with the organization of the Church in the diocese of Wrocław. On 21 January, Fr. Milik was removed from the position of apostolic administrator of the archdiocese, who after being arrested, was interned in the Capuchin monastery in Rywałd, the place of later isolation of primate of Poland Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński. Under pressure from the political authorities, the Wrocław chapter represented by just one person, canon Fr. Franciszek Niedźbała, on 26 January 1951 elected Fr. Kazimierz Lagosz, sympathizing with the communist authorities as vicar general, and to whom Primate Wyszyński was forced to give his canonical consent. Dedication of the rebuilt temple on 29 July 1951, with the participation of the Primate of Poland, should therefore be treated as a document of the Stalinist era. Currently, when visiting the Gothic cathedral, a casual tourist or a faithful of the Wrocław diaspora born in the post-war period can see to a small extent that they are dealing not only with an object erected from the ruins and equipped with altars, organs and decorations being primarily a reminder of the times of reconstruction

⁴ Karol Milik, *Archidiecezja Wroclawska 1945-1951*, „Tygodnik Powszechny”, 1970, 17, p.1; *idem, Archidiecezja wroclawska 1945-1951 (Wspomnienia pierwszego ordynariusza)*, [in:] *Kościół na Ziemiach Zachodnich. Ćwierćwiecze polskiej organizacji kościelnej*, ed. Jan Krucina, Wrocław 1971, p. 49.

⁵ Quoted after: Józef Pater, *Ksiądz infułat dr Karol Milik jako rządcą archidiecezji wroclawskiej w latach 1945-1951*, Wrocław 2012, p. 115; see also Marcinów, *Wokół problemów odbudowy katedry*, p. 322.

⁶ Marcinów, *Wokół problemów odbudowy katedry*, p. 323.

of a seriously damaged city of Wrocław, but also a work marked by the increasing communist terror. Walking around today's Wrocław, there are almost no traces of remembrance that after the period of fanatical defense of the city by fascists (lasting until 6 May 1945) 10 churches were completely destroyed and never rebuilt, while another dozen were damaged to a degree which prevented their use for many years. In the visual sphere, few elements of the cathedral's architecture and décor symbolize the times of its re-erection, but this layer of content is an important element for more insightful audiences.

The visual document of the political situation in Poland, which followed the formation of the consolidated communist party (Polish United Workers' Party – Polska Zjednoczona Partia Robotnicza – PZPR) in December 1948, also remains the cathedral in Katowice. During the reunion of the Polish Socialist Party (Polska Partia Socjalistyczna – PPS) and Polish Workers' Party (Polska Partia Robotnicza – PPR) Aleksander Zawadzki, former Silesian governor and soon deputy prime minister of the government, gave a speech announcing the pursuit of state authorities toward the secularization of social life in Poland. One of the first manifestations of this political program was the suspension of the construction of three new churches in the diocese of Katowice. Several years later, on 26 November 1952, just as in Wrocław, under pressure from the Provincial National Council in Katowice, Fr. Filip Bednorz, favorable to the communist authorities, was elected vicar capitular of the diocese of Katowice⁷. Also in this case, Primate Wyszyński felt compelled to approve the illegally made election on 13 December 1952. After the death of Fr. Bednorz in a car accident, on 21 January 1954 the General Chapter in Katowice elected the next vicar in the person of Fr. Jan Piskorz in the previously applied way, however, under even more pressure from the Security Office and Jerzy Ziętek (deputy chairman of the Voivodship National Council – Wojewódzka Rada Narodowa – WRN – in Katowice). It is currently difficult to identify any positive aspects in the proceedings of the new administrator of the diocese and the completion of Katowice cathedral which was begun before the outbreak of the Second World War is no exception to it. During the reign of Bishop Stanisław Adamski in April 1951, the Provincial Office in Katowice presented a proposal to lower the dome of the cathedral being built. The parish priest of the cathedral

⁷ Jerzy Myszor, *Okoliczności „wyboru” ks. Filipa Bednorza na wikariusza kapitulnego w diecezji katowickiej w listopadzie 1952 roku. Edycja źródeł*, „Śląskie Studia Historyczno-Teologiczne” 2009, 1 (42), pp. 209–212.

Dr. Rudolf Adamczyk, arrested six months later for alleged embezzlement in the construction of the church and equally unlikely spying for the US, refused the proposal put forward by the office, along with the designer of the cathedral, Zygmunt Gawlik. Nevertheless, after Fr. Jan Piskorz took the office of vicar, he came up with a similar project, and despite the opposition of the Chapter and the architect, he implemented his idea and reduced the height of the dome from 95 to 57 m⁸. While the initial design intended for the dome to support the impressive height of the tambour, now its bowl is absurdly low, making the cathedral look far from perfect. In all probability, relatively few people are wondering about the disproportionate shape of the temple, but it is this disharmony that denotes the political and cultural content of a time when the Church is subordinated to the decisions of hostile beliefs of political authorities.

The Cathedrals in Wrocław and Katowice in their formal values, however in a manner that is hardly recognizable to the average viewer, are related to the political circumstances of their creation. The insightful observer can see the simplifications that appeared during the reconstruction of the Gothic temple in Wrocław and the inadequate height of the dome in the classicist and partly modernist church in Katowice. Another case is the two churches in Chorzów: St. Florian and Holy Ghost. In their structural properties they do not have clear traces of non-artistic factors influencing their final shape, nevertheless, both are exceptionally clear testimonies of political changes in Poland.

After October 1956, the communist party and state authorities departed from the Stalinist political system and partially liberalized the political power structure. Throughout Poland, local provincial offices issued 248 permits for the construction and extension of churches up to May 1958. In a large number of these permits, consents were subsequently restricted or withdrawn. In mid-1957, the Communist Party returned to its vision of building a secular state and society, and a year later, in June 1958, a state directive was issued banning offices from issuing permits for the construction of churches. In July 1958, the Central Committee of Polish United Workers' Party issued a document to the local party branches explaining the reasons for stopping the construction of new religious buildings and introduced restrictions on the reconstruction of damaged, historic church buildings or even the extension

⁸ Dorota Głazek, *Historia budowy katedry w Katowicach*, [in:] *Katedra Chrystusa Króla w Katowicach*, eds. Stanisław Puchała, Anna Liskowacka, Katowice 2000, p. 111; Filip Burno, *Zygmunt Gawlik (1895-1961) – architekt katedry katowickiej*, Katowice 2003, pp. 78, 115.

of existing buildings. In response to the petition of the Polish Episcopate of 15 April 1958 protesting against the limitation of construction of new churches, the leader of the party Władysław Gomułka stated that it was an example of incitement of the most backward sections of society against a progressive, socialist state. The party's guidelines directly translated into the conduct of offices and led to the repression of people who were continuing or had tried to start construction.

An example of the implementation of political dispositions towards church builders were activities directed at parish priests of the aforementioned churches in Chorzów. On 30 December 1958, Fr. Karol Nawa, builder of the Holy Spirit church in Chorzów was arrested on suspicion of illegal purchase of building materials, which was treated as a crime in the system of state regulation of industrial products⁹. In the event of an inability to receive an assignment of cement, steel or bricks, the purchasing of this class of goods from private sellers was deemed an offense and threatened with serious fines. The local press attacked the priest, insinuating other crimes in addition, and the Provincial Court in Katowice sentenced him to three years in prison and imposed large fines on 28 January 1961. The construction of the church of St. Florian was facing similar difficulties, where on 20 September 1960, the parish priest Konrad Szweda was arrested and accused of "granting financial benefits to officials in connection with their official duties"¹⁰. In January 1961, temporary detention against him was lifted, but this did not stop the trial on 10 April 1961, resulting in sentencing the accused to eight months in prison. Perhaps the higher punishment and the necessity of serving it were stopped by the fact that the priest was a former prisoner of concentration camps in Auschwitz and Dachau for almost the entire period of the Second World War.

Chorzów churches of St. Florian and the Holy Spirit are outstanding architectural works without structural flaws resulting from the interference of political factors in the final appearance of the object. Halting their construction by administrative decisions and restriction of access to building materials contributed to the long-term construction processes, but ultimately both objects artistically remain neutral in relation to the historical circumstances of their construction. The Church

⁹ Jerzy Nyga, *Bogu i ludziom. Nowe kościoły w diecezji katowickiej*, Katowice 1996, pp. 34–35; Wiktor Skworc, *Budownictwo kościołów w diecezji katowickiej w latach 1945–1989*, Katowice 1996, pp. 88–91.

¹⁰ Nyga, *Bogu i ludziom*, pp. 36–37; Wiktor Skworc, *Budownictwo kościołów na terenie miasta Chorzowa w latach 1945–1970*, [in:] *Z dziejów parafii św. Barbary w Chorzowie*, Chorzów 1998, pp. 52–57; *idem*, *Budownictwo kościołów w diecezji katowickiej*, pp. 88–91.

of St. Florian was built from 9 May 1948 to its consecration on 28 October 1961 and in the following years equipped with bells, organs and stained glass windows. In the post-Conciliar period, the composition of the interior of the temple was changed under the direction of Adam Lisik. Above all, however, the building attracts attention by representing mature architectural modernism with slight influences from pre-war modernized classicism. Also, the interior of the building, although based on the traditional, basilica layout of the extended nave and lower side aisles, awakens admiration with its simplicity and filling with light filtered through stained glass largely based on the principles of abstract painting.

The construction of the church of the Holy Spirit began a decade later, when on 7 December 1958 the cornerstone was laid. Construction works were repeatedly withheld by the state authorities, and as a result, the church was consecrated only on 15 June 1963. The building was not plastered yet, the stained glass was completed in 1975, and two years later organs were installed there. The building represents the next phase of the modernist style, in which some structural elements were highlighted and combined with the influence of expressionistic architecture with certain symbolic values. The external appearance of the church in Chorzów is dominated by high vertical windows of the nave and the massive tower placed in the facade, which by using a long vertical slit repeats the system used in the composition of the nave. Parish administrators, whose reception of the building is reflected in the descriptions of the temple used by them, underlined its symbolic values and comparisons to the appearance of the boat. Nautical associations confirm the partial attachment of the object to the tradition of brutalist architecture, which in the area of sacral architecture was initiated by the corporeal chapel in Le Corbusier's Ronchamp associated with the boat.

It can be concluded that in the present state both analysed churches in Chorzów manifest in their reception primarily sacred values (especially through references to ancient architectural traditions of church buildings), symbolic (through the use of shapes evoking associations with the boat, which is distinctive in Christian symbolism) and artistic (through its high level of architectural designs). In their external appearance, the discussed churches have no references to the fate of religion in the next period of the political history of Poland. This may only indicate the entry of both organizations of social, religious and political-state life into a state of forced co-existence. Nevertheless, all descriptions of objects contained in press, books or Internet publications always emphasize their connections with the fate

of their builders, which makes these works as a whole a cultural document from the time of their creation. The combination of historical knowledge with their material being makes them a form of “a place of remembrance” in spite of the lack of reflections of politics in the sphere of pure visibility.

In the further history of sacred buildings in the area of Lower and Upper Silesia, the tendency to separate religious and political life has been perpetuated. In social life, autonomous values appeared, among which problems related to the ideas of modernism played a special role. It is likely that currently in the study of contemporary history there is too little distance from the times that are described in them, but in spite of such a situation, one may take the risk of proposing some theories about important social life ideas in the early second half of the twentieth century. This period appears to have been dominated by the values of rationality, weakening of the position of tradition, the cult of technology has grown in significance. The official pursuit of secularization and even the very concept of the socialist system may have been something secondary to the universal belief in the power of reason and scientific solving of human and social problems. Not only did communism present itself in publications as scientific, religious values also gained supporters in scientific religious studies promoting the cult of the so-called sacrum, also Christianity has been modernized in its Catholic branch. After the period of fighting modernism both outside the Catholic religion and inside it, the Second Vatican Council led to the modernization of the decisive components of religious rites. The new doctrinal situation was clearly reflected in the formal orders of church buildings and the new organization of internal spaces.

In the Constitution on Sacred Liturgy *Sacrosanctum Concilium*, adopted on 4 December 1963 as the first document of the Second Vatican Council, a statement was made that “the Church did not consider any style as if it were its own, but according to the character and condition of nations and the needs of various rites allowed artistic forms of every era, creating a treasury of art over the centuries, which should be preserved with all care. Also the art of our era and of all nations and regions can freely develop in the Church, if only with due respect and veneration, serve the temples and sacred ceremonies so that it may be able to join this wonderful hymn of praise which in the previous centuries the greatest artists sang in honour of Catholic faith” [SC, 123]. The doctrinal interpretation was accepted as a full admission of architectural and artistic modernism to the needs of the architecture of new churches and changes in the décor of buildings from earlier eras.

In the churches of Upper and Lower Silesia, after the Council, forms taken from industrial architecture appeared, which was already visible in the church of The Holy Spirit in Chorzów, whose view from the side of the presbytery and side elevation can be read as taken from the factory halls. In other facilities, formal components typical of office buildings, houses of culture or residential shop pavilions were applied (Żory, the church of St. Stanislaus, Katowice Szopienice, the Church of Our Lady of Perpetual Help), in both cases the buildings stand out as churches only thanks to the tower attached to the building block.

Ambivalent attitude towards modernism is shown by churches based on their external appearance with the shape of a high, gable roof, typical of old gothic buildings. On one hand, one can notice references to the most enduring traditions of the church building, while on the other hand, bringing the temple to an extremely simple, geometric solution can be considered as desacralizing and proper aesthetics of avant-garde modernism. Such ambiguous arrangements can be found in the Church of Jesus Christ in Chorzów Batory¹¹ and the church of Our Lady in Rydułtowy Orłowiec¹². Sometimes references to more developed roof systems were used, where the upper edges of the roofs are separated and a skylight is created between them, as in the case of St. Jadwiga's church in Rybnik¹³. The popularity of secular bold roof formulas, typical for Felix Candela, Pier Luigi Nervi or Oscar Niemeyer, in the secular architecture, meant that they were also used in churches, but it is impossible to determine their appropriateness in objects of this type. The question "are they an expression of the triumph of engineering approaches to sacralness or, on the contrary, inclusion in the world of religion?" remains without a convincing answer. The lattice ceiling used for industrial or engineering buildings was used in the church of St. Krzysztof in Tychy¹⁴ and the Church of The Pentecost in Siemianowice Śląskie Bytków¹⁵. Maybe it is not a coincidence that in the case of the church in Siemianowice, efforts were later made to partially cover this form of covering in the nave of the church. It can be presumed that it was considered unsuitable for a temple building.

We have a similar, ambiguous situation when the church buildings refer to the shape of a boat or the prow of a ship. The very concept of the main nave of the

¹¹ Nyga, *Bogu i ludziom*, pp. 38–39.

¹² *Ibidem*, pp. 112–113.

¹³ *Ibidem*, pp. 108–109.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, pp. 128–129.

¹⁵ *Ibidem*, pp. 116–117.

church refers to the Latin word *navis* – a boat or a ship, which in old-Christian symbolism referred to the Church, as we find it in Tertullian or *Constitutiones Apostolorum*. At the same time, it should be remembered that modern ships, especially oceanic ones, also the shapes of their engines or turbines, were treated as models for especially secular avant-garde architecture due to their technical advancement. Also in the case of so-called ‘ships prow’ shaped churches which include the objects in Ruda Śląska Halemba (dedicated as *The Birth of Christ*)¹⁶ and in Ruda Śląska (named after St. Pius X)¹⁷, we do not find a definitive answer regarding the question of the ideological content of the church facade formula used. Even the increasing passage of time does not make it easier to solve the problem: if a pattern taken from a world of extremely secular values is included in the pattern of Christian art, then the pattern is Christianized, or the value of saints decreases, so is this desacralization and hidden triumph of rationality over the world of religious values?

A specific problem of the cultural content of churches in Upper and Lower Silesia is the reception of postulates of the liturgical reform movement, which were largely adopted by the Second Vatican Council. The changes introduced focused on raising the importance of the religious community as the proper Church and focusing on the altar identified with Christ himself. Adaptation of these recommendations led to the creation of church blocks and interiors with central plans and to place the altar so that it would be partially surrounded by the faithful. Therefore, plans based on the shape of a circle (or a fragment of a circle) were used, as well as square and polygonal plans. In some versions of the altarocentric space the altar was placed in the corner, the main nave was shortened or the amphitheatre arrangement of the benches was used. A spectacular example of the use of the central plan is the church of Our Lady Queen of Angels in Tychy Wilkowyje. The construction of the temple began in 1958, but the partially constructed walls were demolished on 27 July 1958 with the participation of officers of the Security Office¹⁸. Also the builder of the church, priest Józef Oleś was temporarily arrested. It was only a quarter century later, on 14 April 1981, that the parish received permission for the construction of the church, which was consecrated on 13 October 1988. The largest of the Upper Silesian central churches was built in Tychy Żwaków dedicated as *The*

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, pp. 106–107.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, pp. 104–105.

¹⁸ Cezary Wąs, *Budownictwo kościołów w Polsce po II Wojnie Światowej. Próba syntezy uwa-runkowań politycznych*, „Śląski Kwartalnik Historyczny Sobótka”, 60, 2005, 3, p. 380.

Holy Spirit in the years 1979–1983¹⁹. However, it should be added that buildings with such a plan have always met with the resistance of local priests and a large part of the faithful accustomed to traditional elongated layouts.

A controversial solution to the shape of the part devoted to the faithful was to base it on an amphitheatrical arrangement, appropriate for theatres, music halls and lecture halls. This formula was used in the church Of the Immaculate Heart of the Blessed Virgin Mary in Siechnice near Wrocław, a small building, nevertheless of great historical importance, because the consent to its erection was the first such event in Lower Silesia in the whole period after World War II²⁰. Until 23 February 1971, that is for more than a quarter of a century, administrative authorities did not issue any permission to build a new church in this area. In order to prevent a possible withdrawal of the decision, the design of a church was selected in a competition led by a local branch of the Association of Polish Architects. A situation in which the Wrocław architects' environment was involved in the construction, created a valid reason preventing authorities from stopping the construction process. After the competition and selection of the design by Tadeusz Szukała on 3 August 1973, construction work began and was ended by the consecration of the church on 25 October 1981.

There is no doubt that the political events of December 1970 influenced the official decision in the case of the church in Siechnice. From 14 to 22 December of that year workers' protests broke out against the price increases of many food products in several Polish port cities. The result of the revolt were changes at the top level of party and state authorities, which also prompted another government ruling to make concessions regarding relations with the Church. In the period after December 1970, however, only a few permits were granted, and throughout the next decade, church construction was still not only limited, but also fought with the use of militia. In July 1971, permission was given to build a church in the Gdańsk Przymorze district, whose inhabitants were participants in the tragic events of December 1970. At that time, political events were also a direct reason for issuing permits for the construction of three churches in Wrocław (Holy Spirit, St. Lawrence and the Holy Trinity) as well as the church of the Raising of the Holy Cross in Katowice. In Poland, in 1971, only two permits were issued for the construction of

¹⁹ Andrzej Artur Mroczek, Konrad Kucza-Kuczyński, *Nowe kościoły w Polsce*, Warszawa 1991, p. 18.

²⁰ Wąs, *Budownictwo kościołów w Polsce*. p. 375.

a new sacral building, and in subsequent years until the next political breakthrough in August 1980, the number of positive decisions was equally small. However, the pressure from citizens on the authorities intensified during this period, which over time was encouraged by the election of Cardinal Karol Wojtyła as Pope in 1978.

Buildings erected in the 1970s are in many cases characterized by a high artistic class. The number of objects with outstanding architectural qualities is disproportionately large in relation to the total number of works built in this period. The aesthetic quality of these objects should be treated as their cultural content, because it results from the complex circumstances of their implementation. In almost every case the churches of that time were erected after several decades of waiting for official permission, which led to caution when the official decision to build them was made. They were located in areas where the number of parishioners grew through the creation of new housing estates, which in turn encouraged church investors to plan large-scale facilities. Only those with serious architectural achievements could be appointed to carry out such projects, which in turn resulted in not only projects of large-scale works, but at the same time being outstanding works of architecture. The size and quality of these buildings were therefore not accidental, but they integrated the influence of many historical factors. Involvement of people with high authority in the engineers' environment was also a reason that to some extent prevented obstacles being made by officials in the processes of building the object. The complex games played between construction initiators and the decision-makers opposed to them for political reasons, have never been fully publicly open and were based on formulas that can be difficult to understand. One of such formulas was to ask the authorities for permission to expand the facility, which was easier to obtain than the permission to build a new one, and then expanding the building over the planned sizes. The builders were then brought to court for tort and severely punished with fines, the officials obtained a justification for their superiors, and the object in effect remained in the shape given to it during the alleged expansion. An example of such a situation was enlarging the chapel of the parish of St. Lawrence in Wrocław, formerly serving as a cemetery chapel. After obtaining the permit in 1976 for reconstruction increasing the size of the building by a few meters in 1977–1981, a two-level church with a lofty tower was built according to the design of the well-known Wrocław architect Zenon Nasterski²¹.

²¹ Magdalena Miś, *Wrocławska architektura sakralna z lat 1970-2000*, master thesis under the supervision of Professor Waldemar Okoń, University of Wrocław, 2003, pp. 89–90.

The most outstanding sacral building in Poland in the seventies of the 20th century is The Church of the Holy Spirit in Wrocław, a formally refined work of Tadeusz Zipser, professor of the Wrocław University of Technology, later a rector of this university²². Permission for construction of this object was issued on 16 December 1971, undoubtedly under the influence of the events of December 1970 and after the efforts begun in 1959, aimed first at rebuilding the destroyed parish church and after its demolition in 1967 to build a new one. The famous anecdote in Wrocław regarding the efforts of the parish priest, Stefan Wójcik claims that after another refusal of permission to build, he asked for a passport to travel to Moscow, where a positive decision might be made. A sincere or perhaps false naivety of the cleric hid, however, mockery of Anton Chekhov's story.

The church was founded on a polygon plan with numerous concavities and protrusions. In its external appearance, the temple can be seen as a large brick building modeled on ancient gothic churches but with a decidedly modernized character. A large conch filled with ogival windows was installed above the entrance to the church reinforcing the appeal to the Gothic. This series of connections is continued by the shape of the roof, which repeats the slightly bending line of cupolas of the church of St. Barbara in Kutná Hora, while its two-level structure has its counterpart in the St. John church under the double dedication of Holy Cross and Saint Bartholomew. A set of historical references makes the building one of the first works of postmodernism in Poland with its tendency to use quotations freely. The varied shape of the body also evokes many associations with symbolic and religious connotations. The whole was compared to a decorative casket or even a medieval reliquary. The concavity above the entrance was interpreted as the shape of hands receiving the gifts of the Holy Spirit, to whom this House of God was dedicated. The roof was spoken of as an Old Testament Meeting Tent, in which, according to the will of God, Moses placed the Ark of the Covenant (Ex. 40, 1–3). The return to symbolism strengthens the large altar painting, which depicts scenes illustrating the “Role and activity of the Holy Spirit in the Old and New Testaments”,

²² Tadeusz Zipser, *Kościół św. Ducha we Wrocławiu. Historia kształtowania formy*, [in:] *Architektura Wrocławia*, v. 3, ed. Jerzy Rozpędowski, Politechnika Wrocławska, Wrocław 1997, pp. 465–488; Magdalena Czerepak-Miś, *Kościół pod wezwaniem Ducha Świętego na tle wrocławskich budowli sakralnych końca lat siedemdziesiątych*, bachelor thesis under the supervision of Rafał Eysymontt, University of Wrocław 2001; Miś, *Wrocławska architektura*, pp. 87–88; Ewa Bartosz, *Zrealizowane obiekty sakralne zaprojektowane przez Tadeusza M. Zipsersa*, master thesis under the supervision of Cezary Wąs, University of Wrocław, 2012, pp. 21–33.

among them the amazing representation of a seraph touching the mouth of Isaiah with hot coals (Is 6,6). In the post-war history of Polish churches, the Wrocław facility retains the most-saturated religious content, developed and multiplied by its numerous commentators. Their summary constituted the opinion of Mirosław Drzewiecki, who described the work as a rich *biblium pauperum* and a monument exhibited for the glory of the Third Divine Person²³.

In June 1976, a wave of protests against Poland's communist policy went through Poland. Fearing the widening of rebellious moods, the planned price increases were finally abandoned, and measures were also taken to dissuade the reasons for a further increase in social tensions after a period of violent repression. A clear example of the aspirations to avoid the escalation of social discontent was the granting of permission for the construction of a church on 27 May 1977 by the Governor of Katowice, Stanisław Kiermaszek, for Millennium housing estate in Katowice with 30,000 residents. The authorities' special resistance to this place was caused by the fact that in its ideological assumption it was to be a model socialist settlement deliberately deprived of the church building. The permission for its construction was preceded by a period of several years of efforts to issue it, but it was also the result of promoting information about the state of church construction in the diocese of Silesia during the annual pilgrimage of workers to the sanctuary of the Mother of Justice and Social Love in Piekary Śląskie. Throughout the 1970s, hundreds of thousands of pilgrims learned of the difficulties created by the authorities with regard to the construction of churches, contrary to the practice of maintaining a state monopoly on shaping public opinion.

The construction of the church at the Millennium Housing Estate began on 27 September 1979, and on 13 December 1981, martial law was declared and directed against the Solidarity revolution in Poland. The bishop of Katowice Herbert Bednorz consecrated the lower part of the two-level church and dedicated it to the Mother of God, Healer of The Sick²⁴. The consecration of the upper church took place only ten years later, on 14 September 1991, when the church was dedicated

²³ Mirosław Drzewiecki, *Sakralne bryły i wnętrza*, [in:] *Patientia et caritas: w hołdzie Księdzu Kardynałowi Henrykowi Gulbinowiczowi, Arcybiskupowi, Metropoliecie Wrocławskiemu, w 25 lecie sakry biskupiej*, ed. Ignacy Dec, Wrocław 1995, p. 332.

²⁴ Nyga, *Bogu i ludziom*, pp. 76–77; Andrzej Babuchowski, *Oto drzewo krzyża...*, „Katolik”, 1982, 19, pp. 6–7.

to The Raising of the Holy Cross²⁵. The choice of dedication was intended to commemorate the objectionable destruction of roadside crosses that took place during the construction of the estate and Katowice-Chorzów road. The work of two Silesian architects with immense authority, Henryk Buszko and Aleksander Franta, it directly contrasted the grey, multi-storey residential buildings. The plan of the temple was based on a multitude of curved lines and the walls complementing the reinforced concrete structure were made of dark red brick, from which Upper Silesia was traditionally built in both factory buildings and housing estates. In contrast to the Wrocław church of The Holy Spirit the work from Katowice continues the modernist tradition, especially the so-called brick expressionism. To a lesser extent than Zipser's work it is saturated with symbolism, it nevertheless has the trait of traditionalism and corresponds to the custom of creating a worthy place for religious ceremonies. The decisive factor for the significance of this building is the fact that the elevation itself has clearly changed the character of the whole of its surroundings, not only supplementing them with a sacred element, but also humanizing them by restoring the living traditions familiar to the congregation.

The previous review of the most important Silesian churches of the period after the end of World War II clearly shows that each of them was closely related to the political upheavals that occurred at that time in Poland. An analogous relationship between granting permission for the construction of a new temple and the situation in which the authorities sought to avoid the escalation of social conflict occurred in the case of the Wrocław church of Our Lady the Queen of Peace in the Popowice estate²⁶. The extensive habitat was built in the mid-1970s for 17.5 thousand residents without considering the location of a new church within its area. However, when in August 1980 shipyard workers' strikes began in the shipyards of Gdansk and Gdynia, which were joined by more than 700 enterprises across Poland, the authorities adopted a policy of concessions and signed an agreement with strikers on 31 August accepting the demands made by workers during the negotiations. Because Wrocław became one of the main cities that joined the August protests as early as 20 August 1980, during the intensification of the conflict, the authorities agreed to build a church in Popowice. It was anticipated that by

²⁵ Even the large size of the temple did not allow full satisfaction of pastoral needs and in the eighties it was necessary to build another church in the estate.

²⁶ Michał Kaczmarek, *Parafia Matki Bożej Królowej Pokoju na Popowicach*, Wrocław 1997; Wojciech Jarzabek, *Sacrum, architektura i indywidualność*, „Magazyn Budowlany”, 1997, 2, pp. 12–16; Miś, *Wrocławska architektura*, pp. 96–98.

solving this problem, the involvement of Church representatives on the side of the protesters would decrease, and some of the awakened social enthusiasm would be directed towards non-political activities. A similar policy was applied by authorities throughout Poland, which led to an extraordinary scale of church building in over three thousand Polish cities and towns. The Wrocław church symbolically remains the first of this long sequence of buildings.

The design of the church in Popowice was the result of a competition, which was won by the thirty-year-old architect Wojciech Jarzabek and a group of his colleagues. The form of a square was chosen as the basis for the appearance of the body and all structural and decorative elements, which was transformed and distorted with unprecedented ingenuity. The square that was used to create the portal was brought to a shape resembling a gothic ogive. It is this element of the structure and at the same time the decoration of the church that facilitates understanding of the architect's intentions, which also in a large number of other forms sought to create a link between the distant, medieval traditions of Wrocław's sacred buildings, and exemplary brick expressionism from the 1930s (including the Evangelical church of Gustav Adolf at the Sępolno housing estate) and the completely contemporary current of the so-called Romantic geometry. As a result of this heterogeneous approach, a wide-ranging structure was created, which – as was often the case with representatives of brick expressionism – resembles a Gothic castle, so it can also be a Teutonic castle that used to be the basis of sacred buildings the Vistula-Baltic style. The building has a reinforced concrete skeleton, but on all sides it is covered with a red brick that adds even more to the gothic churches of Wrocław. The roof of the temple was carefully thought out and treated as an additional “fifth elevation” visible from the windows of residential high-rise buildings surrounding the church. Symbolic values were transferred in a way that is distant from figurative ones, however, in connection with the explanations provided by the designers, they may constitute an additional, readable component of the general pronunciation of the church. The split tower completed with the square placed in the corner of the upper part was compared to hands folded for prayer, while the extensive roof with many tracts was described as a soft garment of the patron of the church, under which the faithful find shelter from afflictions of mortality. The traditionalism of the building or the symbolism of its parts are not immediately obvious, but such that their use builds respect not only to the richness of historical references, but also their sophisticated application.

In the period of over a dozen months after reaching agreement between state authorities and representatives of striking workers, conflicts were continually arising from society's desire for further liberalization of the state system on the one hand and on the other hand communist attempts to escape from the freedoms obtained. The situation which left the dispute unambiguously resolved was interrupted by the introduction of the state of emergency on 13 December 1981, which according to the applicable legal system was defined as "martial law". At the beginning of this period, the main official decisions were taken by the so-called military commissioners who were characterized by pragmatism and striving to avoid conflict with church authorities in relation to church construction. The permits obtained at that time, led to the construction of churches in several thousand places throughout Poland. In the new situation, there was no longer a need for large objects, but rather objects adopted to the needs of specific parishes. The trend of establishing the forms of buildings to the most traditional solutions characteristic of sacral architecture, including the use of extended front elevations, high towers and gable roofs, was also strengthened. A characteristic object of the eighties is the church of St. Barbara in Giszowiec – Katowice district²⁷. The permission for construction of the church was obtained in 1983, even before August 1984, a parish was established in this area. The temple, which was consecrated on 23 October 1994, in its appearance resembles a modernized version of a typical neo-gothic parish church in a small town.

The parliamentary elections in June 1989 and the successive change of the political system in Poland took place in a situation where the main needs in the area of church construction were already met. All the activities of building spectacular sacred works after 1989 have lost their connection with political tensions which were caused by the undemocratic and ineffective economic system of the so-called real socialism. Only the Warsaw church of Divine Providence was established by a resolution of parliament in 1998, a memorial to several-year struggles for freedom and independence. References to great historical events in the dioceses of Lower and Upper Silesia also appeared in the case of the Wrocław church of Christ the Redeemer of the World, also referred to as the church-monument of the Millennium of the Wrocław Diocese.

²⁷ Nyga, *Bogu i ludziom*, pp. 72–73.

Wrocław's Metropolitan Curia announced in 1990 a competition for the construction of a temple, which was supposed to commemorate the establishment in the year 1000 of a diocese subordinated to the metropolis of Gniezno. The winning design by Jadwiga Grabowska-Hawrylak assumed the erection of a building, which was supposed to refer to the gothic cathedral of the archdiocese of the city, St. John the Baptist and like the prototype was to stand out with its impressive two-storied facade. Using the pattern of the old building was the main element in creating the ideological meaning of the work and the content held therein regarding the positive assessment of the importance of continuity in the functioning of religious and national communities. However, a more thorough analysis may disturb this opinion. Michał Duda, researcher for the work of the author of the project, drew attention to the influence of Kisho Kurokawa (in relation to using the lattice motif) and Aldo Rossi (in the case of characteristic small windows in the side walls of the facade)²⁸. The lattice crowning one tower and penetrating the second tower, was a characteristic form of the architecture of late modernism and contained a reflection on the structures typical of the modernist style. Similarly self-reflective was Rossi's entire work suspended between the anguish of late modernism and postmodern historicism. Thus, reflections on artistic problems appropriate to times of weariness in modernism and, at the same time, fears of rejection of it in favour of another, barren traditionalism, were written into the object of such a historical importance.

The history of ideological content of sacred buildings in Lower and Upper Silesia in the period after the end of World War II begins with the restoration of the Gothic cathedral in Wrocław and ends with the building, which is modelled on it. The historical space between these two buildings is filled with objects that were seriously affected by political events. Some of these incidents have left traces in the forms of these buildings, while others have rather been imprinted in the texts about the circumstances of their construction. It should be noted, however, that the last of the works discussed here, changes the political theme to consider the prospects for further development of modern societies in which religious cults no longer play an important role, by supplementing historical references with research into the problems of modernist architecture.

²⁸ Michał Duda, *Patchwork. Architektura Jadwigi Grabowskiej-Hawrylak*, Wrocław 2016, p. 252.

TREŚCI KULTUROWE WYBITNYCH DZIEŁ ARCHITEKTURY SAKRALNEJ NA ŚLĄSKU W LATACH 1945–2015

STRESZCZENIE

Historia budowli sakralnych na Dolnym i Górnym Śląsku w okresie po zakończeniu II wojny światowej rozpoczyna się od odbudowy gotyckiej katedry we Wrocławiu, zniszczonej podczas oblężenia Wrocławia przez Armię Czerwoną wiosną 1945 r. Renowacja katedry w latach 1946–1949 miała miejsce w warunkach walki partii komunistycznej o uzyskanie pełnej władzy politycznej i dążenia do osłabienia roli Kościoła. W 1951 r. władze państwowe ingerowały w strukturę Kościoła poprzez wybór na wikariusza generalnego osoby uległej nowemu systemowi państwowemu. Konsekracja odrestaurowanej katedry św. Jana Chrzciciela w 1951 r. odbyła się zatem w czasie intensyfikacji terroru komunistycznego i obecnie może być również uważana za część zbiorowej pamięci czasów stalinizmu. Wszystkie ważne dzieła architektury sakralnej zbudowane w późniejszych latach wiązały się w podobny sposób z wydarzeniami politycznymi w Polsce. Po październiku 1956 r., kiedy zakończyła się pierwsza faza liberalizacji systemu socjalistycznego, władze początkowo wydały pozwolenia na budowę nowych kościołów, ale wkrótce powróciły do swojej wizji budowy całkowicie świeckiego społeczeństwa. Plany zakładania nowych kościołów traktowano jako podżeganie zacofanych mas do walki przeciwko nowoczesnemu państwu. Duchowni budujący kościoły byli aresztowani pod fałszywymi zarzutami. Gdy udało im się ukończyć wzniesione obiekty, częścią ich ideologicznej treści jest pamięć o prześladowaniu ich budowniczych (Chorzów: kościół św. Floriana i kościół św. Ducha).

Kolejne fale budowania nowych kościołów miały miejsce po tragicznych wydarzeniach z grudnia 1970 r. (kościół w Siechnicach pod Wrocławiem, kościół Ducha Świętego we Wrocławiu), po fali protestów w czerwcu 1976 r. (kościół na osiedlu millennialnym w Katowicach), po rewolucji Solidarności w sierpniu 1980 r. (kościół na osiedlu Popowice we Wrocławiu). Po ogłoszeniu stanu wojennego w grudniu 1981 r. komisarze wojskowi starali się unikać napięć społecznych i masowo udzielali pozwoleń na wnoszenie tysięcy budowli sakralnych w całej Polsce. Charakterystyczną budowlą tego okresu jest kościół św. Barbary w dzielnicy Giszowiec – Katowice. Gdy w czerwcu 1989 r. zmienił się system polityczny w Polsce, większość potrzeb w sferze budownictwa sakralnego została zaspokojona. Historię kolejnych okresów budowy nowych kościołów, które zawsze były zakorzenione w tragicznych wydarzeniach historycznych, zamyka Kościół Chrystusa Odkupiciela Świata, pierwszy od pół wieku nie związany z wydarzeniami politycznymi w Polsce.

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ŚLĄSKI KWARTALNIK HISTORYCZNY SOBÓTKA

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